

THE MAIN COMPONENTS OF CORRECT COMMUNICATION IN THE STUDIED LANGUAGE AND WAYS OF THEIR FORMATION

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the importance of accuracy and fluency in effective communication. Also, which of these components serve as the main source for intelligible and reliable speech and my thoughts on their development systems are highlighted. The results of my observations and the methods of scientific researchers are cited in the article.

Key words: *speech, communication, accuracy, freedom, fluency, grammatical rules, vocabulary, pronunciation, continuity.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье обсуждается важность точности и беглости в эффективном общении. Также, какие из этих компонентов служат основным источником для внятной и достоверной речи и выделены мои мысли по их системам развития. В статье цитируются результаты моих наблюдений и методы научных исследователей.

Ключевые слова и фразы: *речь, общение, точность, свобода, беглость, грамматические правила, словарный запас, произношение, непрерывность.*

INTRODUCTION

Learning a language is an important factor of world discoveries, news, scientific achievements, in short, awareness of new world movements, expansion of worldview. Today, almost every young person who wants to become an expert in their field is interested in learning a language. As science develops, the tendency of students, researchers and amateurs to follow this progress is also increasing. Knowing the key to progress and making new discoveries requires learning a language nowadays. The more correctly the language is mastered, the more productive the result. Therefore, the issue of increasing efficiency in the language is being discussed by language researchers.

It is not unusual place expertise that human lifestyles, hobby and communicate presuppose the lifestyles of statistics with inside the shape of textual content. As scientists note, the flip of linguistics to the textual content has turned out to be a revolution in linguistics [7, 19]. The characteristic of the textual content is sense-forming, communicative and creative. Within the framework of the applicable query for linguistics approximately the interplay of language, speech, textual content, we take into account valid the definition of A.E. Suprun that the textual content is a shape of language lifestyles [8, 154]. Based at the dialectic of the connection among language and speech, many pupils comply with that the textual content is each a speech and language phenomenon. On the one hand, «the textual content refers back to the gadget of language units, i.e. to the language, and at the other — to the communicative act» [7, 25].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Observance of accuracy in speech means adherence to grammatical rules, correct use of the available vocabulary, i.e., the correct use of words in it, even the correct use of word levels and types, and thinking of sentences in terms of their essence. , means to use instead. And fluency requires smoothness, continuity and confidence in speech. It is known from the meanings that these aspects are the main means of speech. But it is not always possible to embody both during communication. For this reason, it has

become a matter of discussion which of them is more important for clear and effective communication.

The importance of accuracy in communication

Clarity in speech is definitely the main component of communication. Correctly formed speech ensures that the communication also goes in the correct form. We all know that correct pronunciation and correct application of sentences without mistakes is a key to efficiency. These tools are important in forming a correct understanding of the person with whom we are communicating. Accuracy shows what level we are in the language being studied. The more accurate the language, the higher the result. In today's widely used language level test, i.e. IELTS, examiners are focusing on accuracy. All their efforts are spent on paying attention to every detail, that is, perfecting the use of tenses in speech, trying to use difficult levels of words, using non-repeating types, and making pronunciation at a high level. These contents are expected to bring them high marks in the exam.

The importance of fluency in communication

Language fluency is also considered a key component in communication in terms of importance. Attention to every detail is not considered the main part of this content. Continuity in communication, that is, keeping it in the same direction with confidence, is important for achieving effectiveness. In grammar, perfect and difficult words are not clear when using intermediate or simple words, and continuous and confident communication is useful, focusing on the main parts of the rules. Focusing on every aspect creates confusion. The intended result may show the complete opposite. Attention to detail can change the tone of an entire speech. The tools learned to follow each rule correctly and use difficult and colorful words often become an obstacle to using them properly. Many learned terms and words cannot be accepted by the human brain in the same way. Even in the remembered situation, which of them to use at what time is often a problem.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to my observations in one of the university classes, freedom of communication is the most important tool. This means that when the student communicates without fear of making mistakes in speech, he feels free and develops fluency, continuity and boldness. Able to demonstrate intelligible speech, although not completely correct. The lesson was conducted by an English teacher of English nationality. The atmosphere created by the teacher in the classroom is friendly and based on independent feedback. There are no rules that students must strictly follow. Deficiencies in their language skills were addressed gently and through appropriate tools and techniques. An opportunity was given to exchange ideas in pairs on each introduced topic. A language environment has been created for them to communicate freely in the language they are learning. What is important is that students demonstrate fluency without any hesitation or anxiety.

The problems in the results of the research carried out by Nurul Masyithah, a student of the Department of English Language Education of Ar-Raniri State Islamic University, are almost similar to the problems mentioned above. The researcher probed the students' opinions with two questions. These are:

1. Strategies used in the development of fluent speech;
2. Difficulties in communicating in English [8, 45].

The results show that listening to English songs more, watching videos, communicating in pairs during the lesson, constantly writing down information, and several other methods help to develop English speaking. The main obstacles to speaking fluently are nervousness in communication, lack of support from teammates, lack of internal motivation, overthinking about grammatical rules, and difficulty in pronunciation. Nurul Masyithah's research results are almost similar to the opinions of several other famous researchers, and she brings this similarity in her work [8, 50]. Zhang, one of the well-known researchers, stated that speaking a new language is the most difficult skill to master [11, 93]. Of course, this is a process that requires a lot of skill and time. Also, another researcher, Ur expressed his opinion about the factors that

cause many difficulties in the formation and development of speech skills [9, 34]. These factors, as I mentioned above, are the student's anxiety and hesitation during the communication process, their fear of being criticized for their mistakes, and their sense of shyness.

CONCLUSION

Speech requires precision in some aspects and fluency in others. Neglecting fluency in pursuit of the goal of communicating in the right way in every way will definitely reduce productivity. The main thing is to be able to use each tool in its place.

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